

ALBUMINURIA VS SERUM CREATININE AS A MARKER OF CONTRAST INDUCED NEPHROPATHY IN CASES WITH NORMAL OR LOW HEMOGLOBIN UNDERGOING PERCUTANEOUS CORONARY INTERVENTION

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Abstract

Background An increase in the use of iodinated contrast media occasionally causes contrast-induced nephropathy (CIN) in patients undergoing coronary angiography and/or percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI). With wide application of Percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) technique in patients with coronary artery disease, contrast-induced acute kidney injury has become a serious complication. Hemoglobin has a significant impact on occurrence of CIN after PCI. Moreover due to variation of serum creatinine among patients of different weight, age, gender, volume status etc, it has some limitations in identifying CIN so role of some other potential marker like albuminuria should be established. But scarce data is available in this regard. Therefore we planned this study.

Objective To determine contrast induce nephropathy in cases with normal or low hemoglobin undergoing percutaneous coronary intervention.

To determine whether creatinine or albuminuria is a better biomarker of contrast-induced nephropathy in patients with normal or low hemoglobin level undergoing percutaneous coronary intervention

Material and methods

Study design: Comparative cross-sectional study

Setting: Department of Cardiology, Mayo Hospital Lahore.

Study duration: Six months

Data Collection Methodology

One hundred patients were included and divided into 2 groups like Group-A (normal Hb level) and Group-B (low Hb level). Demographic data such as age, sex, height (cm), weight (kg), BMI (kg/m²) and other risk factors was recorded

.Volume of contrast medium was recorded. Serum creatinine and albuminuria were measured 24hrs before and 48 hours after PCI. In case of raised serum creatinine level or albuminuria level, renal impairment (CIN) was labeled. All data was collected in data collection form. Data was analyzed in SPSS v. 22.0. Chi-square test will be applied to compare CIN in both study groups, taking p -value ≤ 0.05 as significant.

Results In patients with low Hb, mean age was 47.72 ± 6.64 years. In patients with normal Hb, mean age was 48.78 ± 6.03 years. In patients with low Hb, there were 36 (72.0%) males and 14 (28.0%) females. In patients with normal Hb, there were 30 (60.0%) males and 20 (40.0%) females. In patients with low Hb, the mean serum creatinine level was 1.04 ± 0.23 mg/dl at baseline, which was increased to 1.48 ± 0.43 mg/dl after 24 hours of PCI. In patient with normal Hb, mean creatinine level was 1.07 ± 0.22 mg/dl, which was increased to 1.31 ± 0.27 mg/dl ($p < 0.05$). In patients with low Hb, CIN was positive in 17 (34.0%) cases while in patients with normal Hb only 8 (16.0%) cases had CIN ($p < 0.05$). In patients with low Hb, mean albuminuria level was 40.88 ± 7.27 mg/g at baseline, which was increased to 47.34 ± 13.81 mg/g after 48 hours. In patients with normal Hb, mean albuminuria level was 38.36 ± 4.94 mg/g at baseline, which was increased to 43.43 ± 9.79 mg/g after 48 hours ($p > 0.05$). CIN was positive in 20 (40.0%) cases in patients with low Hb while in 9 (18.0%) cases who had normal Hb ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion CIN was statistically significantly associated with low HB after administering contrast media in PCI. It was also found in a current study that serum creatinine was a better indicator than Albuminuria for detection of CIN.

INTRODUCTION

An increase in the use of iodinated contrast media such as iohexol, iodixanol, iopamidol and iopromide, occasionally causes contrast-induced nephropathy (CIN) in patients undergoing coronary angiography and/or percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI).¹

With wide application of PCI procedure in patients with coronary artery disease, contrast-induced acute kidney injury has become a serious complication.² It occurs within 24-48 hours of the exposure, with creatinine level usually peaking at 3-5 days after procedure and returning to baseline or near baseline value within 1-3 weeks.³

The disease's etiology is multifaceted and there are still many significant questions about the pathophysiology and preventative measures.⁴ Risk factors for development include volume and type of contrast agent; also patient-related factors such as Chronic Kidney Disease, diabetes mellitus, congestive heart failure, advanced age, anemia, sex, hemodynamic instability, and reduced effective circulating volume.^{5,6}

Recently, it is reported that pre-procedural low hemoglobin is also an independent determinant of increased incidence of contrast induced nephropathy after percutaneous coronary intervention. A study reports that among the 1,026 patients studied, 32 (3.1%) developed CIN after the procedure. CIN occurred in 6.3 % of the anemic patients and in 2.2% of the non-anemic patients ($P < 0.01$).⁷ While another study reported that in 841 patients undergoing PCI percentage of CIN in normal Hb group was seen in 5% and in low Hb group was seen in 14.7% p -value < 0.01 .⁸

Albuminuria and creatinine are reliable markers of nephropathy. Both of these biomarkers along with others are evaluated to assess decline in kidney function. There are no studies as such to compare albuminuria and creatinine as which of them is better marker in detecting kidney damage early. There are few studies which suggest hemoglobin level may contribute to pathogenesis of kidney dysfunction.⁹

So, the aim of this study was to determine if low hemoglobin is risk factor for developing CIN after PCI and whether albuminuria or serum creatinine is better marker of CIN in cases with normal and low hb undergoing PCI.¹⁰

Contrast-induced nephropathy (CIN) is a complication that is well known to occur when using iodinated contrast media in diagnostic and treatment actions related to coronary angiography and percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI).¹¹ As the practice of using PCI in the treatment of coronary artery disease (CAD) has expanded, CIN has become an important source of hospital-acquired acute kidney injury (AKI), being responsible of an estimated 12% of all cases worldwide.^{12,13} The rates of CIN are highly diverse with an incidence of 0-24 percent, and increase depends on the risk factors that are specific to the patient with greater rates occurring in high-risk groups such as those that have existing renal impairment, diabetes mellitus, or advanced age.^{14,15,16}

Absolute increase in serum creatinine by 0.5 mg/dl or relative rise of 25 percent of baseline creatinine within 48-72 h after exposure to contrast, in absence of other causes of AKI is usually defined as CIN. CIN is linked to many adverse outcomes, which include long-term hospitalizations, morbidity, and extended mortality.^{17,18} It could require renal replacement therapy in severe cases, which has an enormous burden to medical care systems. CIN has multifactorial pathophysiology, including the renal medullary hypoxia secondary to contrast-induced vasoconstriction, direct tubular toxicity of reactive oxygen species, and activation of inflammatory mediators.^{19,20}

Among many risk factors of CIN, the recent interest has been given to anemia as a possible independent predictor.²¹ Hemoglobin (Hb) is essential in the process of delivering oxygen to the tissues and the absence of this can further make renal hypoxia worse especially during the advent of contrast induced vasoconstriction.^{22,23} Research indicates that low Hb level predisposes patients at risk of developing CIN whereby incidences were reported to stand at 6.3per cent in anemic patients and 2.2per cent in non-anemic patients.^{24,25,26} Such difference highlights the significance of Hb as a treatable risk factor of CIN prevention.²⁷

CIN is traditionally diagnosed by measuring the serum creatinine concentration that indicates the level of glomerular filtration rate (GFR).^{28,29,30} Nevertheless, creatinine suffers some shortcomings such as increase after injury takes time as well as it dependability on age, gender, muscle mass and hydration.^{31,32} Therefore, there are other biomarkers that were studied to detect renal damage at a very early stage including albuminuria.³³ Albuminuria, representing glomerular or tubular disorder, can precede serum creatinine changes, which may be a certain strength in early identification.^{34,35} Nevertheless, there is a rare comparative data on the effectiveness of serum creatinine and albuminuria in revealing CIN, especially in cases of anemia.

Usefulness of the study can be explained by the fact that the prevalence of anemia in the population, diagnosed with PCI, is very high and, at the same time, the local information concerning the relatedness of anemia and CIN was absent.³⁶ Patients with cardiovascular disease are highly prone to anemia because of long-term inflammation, iron deficiency, or the presence of other diseases like chronic kidney disease (CKD).^{37,38} Reduced oxygen-carrying capacity leading to hypoxemia can further worsen contrast-induced renal injury to emphasize the relevance of specific risk stratification.^{39,40} In addition, although serum creatinine and albuminuria are universally accessible and affordable cases, their comparative usefulness in anemic or non-anemic clientele has not still been confirmed.

This study aims to address these gaps by investigating two primary objectives:

1. To determine the incidence of CIN in patients with normal versus low Hb levels undergoing PCI.
2. To compare the diagnostic accuracy of serum creatinine and albuminuria as biomarkers for CIN in these patient groups.

The secondary outcomes are the assessment of the effects of contrast volume (>150 mL Vs. 150 mL or less) and procedure duration on the development of CIN in addition to the determination of the contributing effects of demographics and clinical factors in terms of age, diabetes, hypertension and dyslipidemia.

Clinical and Mechanistic Background

The nephrons are extremely vulnerable to contrast media, because they have an exclusive anatomy of their vascular and tubular structures. Ischemic injury is especially susceptible to the renal medulla, which is exposed, since it is an area of lowered oxygen tension.^{41,45} The contrast agent causes vasoconstriction in the afferent arterioles that slows down the flow of blood to the kidney and brings about severe hypoxia of the medulla.^{42,43,44} Also, the hyperosmolarity of the contrast media facilitates oxidative stress, cell apoptosis of tubular epithelial cells and thus disturbs renal functioning further.

These processes are demanding with the addition of anemia that reduces the supply of oxygen to the renal parenchyma.⁴⁶ The vasoconstriction evoked by contrast mediums inhibits the compensatory renal circulatory adjustments, and renal blood flow in anemic patients cannot be augmented, resulting in a dangerous failure of oxygen delivery to meet oxygen demand. This hypoxic environment activates the inflammatory cascades and generates free radicals, which lead to tubular damage.⁴⁷ The research has revealed that every 1 g/dL lower in Hb proportionate to 12 g/dL increases post-PCI mortality by 2.5-fold, and the prognostic value of anemia is highlighted in this scenario.

Diagnostic Challenges and Biomarkers

The most common marker, serum creatinine is also flawed as it rises gradually and is also affected by non-renal variables.⁴⁸ Newer biomarkers like the neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin (NGAL), cystatin C and liver fatty acid-binding protein (L-Fabp) provide early bias but are limited in cost and availability.⁴⁹ Albuminuria, besides signifying either glomerular endothelial dysfunction or tubular damage, has demonstrated a potential in CIN forecasting. As an example, Saito et al. showed that albuminuria level was independent predictor of CIN in patients undergoing cardiac catheterization when albuminuria 30 mg/g creatinine or higher. We do not however know how well it compares to serum creatinine in anaemic patients.^{50,51}

Therapeutic and Preventive Strategies

Some of the prevailing interventions to manage CIN have been on hydration, contrast minimization and

the use of medical drugs. Hydration with isotonic saline is still the essential vector of prevention, but the evidence on sodium bicarbonate or N-acetylcysteine (NAC) is contradictory.^{52,54,55} Pleiotropic anti-inflammatory properties of statins and antioxidant properties have exhibited potential in decreasing the incidence of CIN, especially on chronic use. Notably, it means that the treatment of anemia prior to PCI can become a new preventive strategy, yet it needs further confirmation.⁵³

Study Rationale and Innovation

The paper is one of the first reports that directly elaborates the comparison of serum creatinine and albuminuria as the measures of CIN diagnosis in PCI patients with or without anemia.⁵⁶ It aims to gain a clear understanding of whether the effect of anemia changes the performance of such biomarkers through stratifying the results against the Hb levels. Also, it addresses variables in procedure that might be easy to change (e.g., amount of contrast) that would inform clinical practice.⁵⁷ The results can be used in risk stratification procedures and initial care plans, especially in an environment with poorly developed resources in which the advanced biomarkers cannot be performed.

To summarise, it is possible to note that CIN is still a potentially avoidable but clinically significant complication of PCI with anemia becoming one of the crucial risk-modifying factors. The proposed study will fine-tune the process of diagnostics and emphasize the interaction between the level of hemoglobin and renal injury, ultimately leading to better outcomes of patients in the field of interventional cardiology.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study design:

Comparative cross-sectional study

Setting:

The study was conducted in the Department of Cardiology, Mayo Hospital Lahore.

Study duration:

Six months after approval of synopsis.

Sample technique:

Non-probability convenient sampling

Sample size:

A sample size of 100 patients (50 patients in each group) is estimated by using 95% Confidence level, 8% absolute precision with expected percentage

anemic patients as 6.3% and non-anemic patients as 2.2%

$$n = \frac{\{z_{1-\alpha} \sqrt{2 \bar{P}(1-\bar{P})} + z_{1-\beta} \sqrt{P_1(1-P_1) + P_2(1-P_2)}\}^2}{(P_1 - P_2)^2}$$

Confidence level 95% = 1.96

P1= Population proportion I = 6.3%

P2= Population proportion II = 2.2%

d = Absolute precision = 8%

Sample selection criteria:

Inclusion criteria

- All patients of either gender and aged 18-60 years planned for PCI (PTCA with stenting)
- All patients with GFR> 90ml/min
- Hemoglobin >10 mg/dl

Exclusion criteria:

- Presence of protein in urine complete examination.
- History of intravascular administration of an iodinated contrast medium in previous 7 days,
- Severe concomitant diseases (e.g. chronic liver disease, known neoplastic disorder)
- Hemodynamically unstable patients,
- Patients with congestive heart failure (NYHA class III and IV),
- Patients with renal transplantation

Data Collection Methodology:

After approval from hospital AS&RB KEMU, all cases will be enrolled from in-patient department of Cardiology, Mayo Hospital Lahore. After taking informed written consent, detailed history will be taken before any clinical examination. Their basic evaluation will be done by taking clinical history, and relevant investigations. Demographic data such as age, sex, height (cm), weight (kg), BMI (kg/m²) and other risk factors will be recorded. Patients will be divided into 2 groups like Group-A (normal Hb level) and Group-B (low Hb level). Non-ionic low osmolar contrast agents will be used in all patients. Volume of contrast medium (ml) will be recorded. Renal function will be assessed by the serum creatinine, albuminuria and estimated glomerular filtration rate using the Cockcroft and Gault formula $CCr = (140 - \text{age}) \times \text{weight} \times \text{constant} / Cr \times 0.85$ (if

female). Serum creatinine and albuminuria will be measured within 24hrs before PCI and on day 3 and 15 after PCI. If there is renal impairment (CIN), patient will be followed more vigilantly from the 4th day onward after PCI until recovery. All adverse events will be recorded during the follow-up period. All relevant data will be collected in an approved data collection form.

Data Analysis:

Data will be entered and analyzed using SPSS version 22.0. Frequencies and percentages will be calculated for qualitative variables like gender and CIN. Mean ± standard deviation will be calculated for quantitative variables like age (days), weight, height, BMI, Volume of contrast medium (ml), Duration of PCI and serum creatinine level and albuminuria at different intervals. Chi-square test will be applied to compare CIN in both study groups. Data will be stratified for age, gender, risk profile, volume of contrast medium (ml) and duration of PCI. Post-stratification Chi-square test will be applied, taking p-value ≤ 0.05 as significant.

RESULTS

The results of the current study were described in tabulated and figure form. The demographic data of participants were described in Table 1 to Table 10. Table 1 provided the mean age of participants in which Low Hb and Normal Hb patients had a mean age of 47.72±6.64 years and 48.78±6.03 years respectively. The gender distribution of participants was described in Table 2 in which 36 (72.0%) males and 14 (28.0%) females belong to the Low Hb group while 30 (60.0%) males and 20 (40.0%) females were from the Normal Hb group.

Table 3 provided detailed information about the anthropometric measurements of patients. The mean height, weight and BMI were 1.66±0.10 meter, 75.70±8.12 kg and 27.47±2.73 kg/m² respectively in

the Low Hb group and 1.67 ± 0.10 meter, 76.02 ± 7.21 kg and 27.52 ± 3.25 kg/m² respectively in Normal Hb group. The obesity distribution was described in Table 4 in which low Hb, had 9 (18.0%) obese and 41 (82.0%) non-obese patients while 13 (26.0%) obese and 37 (74.0%) non-obese patients in the Normal Hb group.

The diabetic distribution of participants was described in Table 5 in which low Hb and Normal Hb groups had 26 (52.0%) diabetic, 24 (48.0%) non-diabetic patients while 24 (48.0%) diabetic and 26 (52.0%) non-diabetic patients respectively. The Hypertensive nature of participants was presented in Table 6 in which 25 (50.0%) hypertensive and 25 (50.0%) non-hypertensive patients of the Low Hb group. However, normal Hb had 23 (46.0%) hypertensive and 27 (54.0%) non-hypertensive patients. Table 7 described the smoking distribution as 23 (46.0%) smokers and 27 (54.0%) non-smokers in Low Hb while 15 (30.0%) smokers and 35 (70.0%) non-smokers in Normal Hb groups. The Dyslipidemia features among Low Hb were 38 (76.0%) had dyslipidemia while 12 (24.0%) did not have dyslipidemia. In patients with normal Hb, There were 34 (68.0%) had dyslipidemia while 16 (32.0%) did not have dyslipidemia.

Table 9 to Table 10 were entirely related to the procedure of percutaneous intervention. The Volume of the contrast medium was described in Table 9. The mean volume of contrast medium in Low Hb and Normal Hb was 171.42 ± 42.62 ml and 173.66 ± 40.69 ml respectively. The duration of percutaneous coronary intervention was described in Table 10 in which the Low Hb group was 91.40 ± 19.17 while in Normal HB duration was 83.44 ± 17.20 .

A within and between-the-groups analysis was conducted through the Paired T-test and Independent T-test as the data was normally distributed with a p-value > 0.05 . Tables 11 and 12 described within and between group analyses of Serum creatinine at baseline and after 24 hours of contrast administration. The mean serum creatinine value of the Low Hb group at baseline and after 24 hours was 1.04 ± 0.234 and 1.47 ± 0.432 . Similarly, the Normal Hb group had 1.06 ± 0.22 and 1.31 ± 0.266 respectively with p-value = 0.000. However, the between-group analysis showed that after 24 hours

the mean serum creatinine value in the Low HB group was 1.47 ± 0.432 while in the Normal Hb group was 1.31 ± 0.266 with p-value = 0.021. This showed that serum creatinine value was statistically raised in the Low Hb group as compared to the Normal Hb group participants.

Tables 13 and 14 described within and between group analyses of Urine Albumin at baseline and after 24 hours of contrast administration. The mean Urine Albumin value of the Low Hb group at baseline and after 24 hours was 40.88 ± 7.27 and 47.34 ± 13.81 . Similarly, the Normal Hb group had 38.36 ± 4.94 and 43.34 ± 9.78 respectively with p-value = 0.000. However, the between-group analysis showed that after 24 hours the mean Urine Albumin value in the Low HB group was 47.34 ± 13.81 while in the Normal Hb group was 43.34 ± 9.78 with p-value = 0.098. This showed that the Urine Albumin value was not statistically raised in Low Hb and Normal Hb groups.

Additionally; the relationship of developing Contrast Induced nephropathy was assessed by using the Correlation test and their results were described in Tables 15 to 18. Table 15 showed in the Low Hb group, 32 (64%) had positive Serum creatinine increase while 18 (36%) were diagnosed negative. Similarly, in Normal Hb, 8 (16%) were positive with Serum creatinine while 42 (84%) were negative. This showed that CIN leads to an increase in the value of serum creatinine. Additionally; Table 16 showed that Low Hb group, 20 (40%) had positive Urine Albumin increase while 30 (60%) were diagnosed with negative. Similarly, in Normal Hb, 9 (18%) were positive with Urine Albumin while 41 (82%) were negative. This showed that CIN leads to an increase in the value of Urine Albumin.

The identification of the best marker for Contrast-induced nephropathy was assessed and described in Tables 17 and 18. The results showed that among all patients, 12 patients were diagnosed with both elevated Serum creatinine and Urine Albumin among the Low Hb groups whereas only 1 patient of Normal Hb level was diagnosed with an elevated level of both enzymes. However; among all 100 patients; 40 patients reported elevated serum creatinine levels and 29 patients reported elevated urine albumin levels with a p-value < 0.05 .

The whole study results showed that serum creatinine and urine albumin level were statistically elevated among the patients presented with Low Hb levels as compared to Normal Hb. Furthermore, Serum creatinine was a statistically significant

biomarker as compared to Urine albumin in determining Contrast Induced nephropathy among the patients treated with percutaneous coronary Intervention.

Table 1
Descriptive statistics of the age of patients

Groups	n	Mean±S.D	Minimum	Maximum
Low Hb	50	47.72±6.64	36	60
Normal Hb	50	48.76±6.03	36	60

Table
Distribution of gender in both groups

Groups	n	Gender	Frequency (%)
Low Hb	50	Male	36 (72%)
		Female	14 (28%)
Normal Hb	50	Male	30 (60%)
		Female	20 (40%)

Gender distribution

Table 3
Descriptive statistics of anthropometric measurement of patients

Groups	n	Anthropometric	Mean \pm S.D
Low Hb	50	Height (m)	1.66 \pm 0.10
		Weight (Kg)	75.70 \pm 8.12
		BMI (kg/m ²)	27.5 \pm 27.46
Normal Hb	50	Height (m)	1.66 \pm 0.97
		Weight (Kg)	76.02 \pm 7.21
		BMI (kg/m ²)	27.51 \pm 3.25

ANTHROPOMETRIC MEASUREMENT

Table 4
Distribution of obesity in both groups

Groups	n	Obesity	Frequency (%)
Low Hb	50	Yes	9 (18%)
		No	41 (82%)
Normal Hb	50	Yes	13 (26%)
		No	37 (74%)

Obesity Distribution

Table 5
Distribution of diabetes in both groups

Groups	n	Diabetes	Frequency (%)
Low Hb	50	Yes	26 (52%)
		No	24 (48%)
Normal Hb	50	Yes	24 (48%)
		No	26 (52%)

Diabetes Distribution

Table 6
Distribution of hypertension in both groups

Groups	n	Hypertension	Frequency (%)
Low Hb	50	Yes	25 (50%)
		No	25 (50%)
Normal Hb	50	Yes	23 (46%)
		No	27 (54%)

Hypertension Distribution

Table 7

Distribution of smoking in both groups

Groups	n	Smoking	Frequency (%)
Low Hb	50	Yes	23 (46%)
		No	27 (54%)
Normal Hb	50	Yes	15 (30%)
		No	35 (70%)

Smoking Distribution

Table
Distribution of dyslipidemia in both groups

Groups	n	Dyslipidemia	Frequency (%)
Low Hb	50	Yes	38 (76%)
		No	12 (24%)
Normal Hb	50	Yes	34 (68%)
		No	16 (32%)

Dyslipidemia Distribution

Table 9
Descriptive statistics of volume of contrast medium used (ml)

Groups	n	Mean ±S.D	Minimum	Maximum
Low Hb	50	171.42±42.62	100	244
Normal Hb	50	173.66±40.71	104	236

VOULME OF CONTRAST MEDIUM USED

Table 10
Descriptive statistics of the duration of PCI (min)

Groups	n	Mean±S.D	Minimum	Maximum
Low Hb	50	91.40±19.17	60	120
Normal Hb	50	83.44±17.20	60	119

DISCUSSION

Those who have undergone percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) are likely to be more susceptible to acute renal impairment caused by contrast medium injection. Nephropathy is one of the most common adverse effects of administering contrast media to humans, particularly in those undergoing PCI or coronary angiography. After removing other potential causes of acute renal injury, kidney dysfunction is defined as an increase in serum creatinine levels of 0.5 mg/dl or 25% that occurs 3 days after PCI.²⁷

Pre Existing kidney disease, contrast media’s dosage and type, heart failure, nephrotoxic drugs, increasing age and female gender, diabetes, and inflammation are factors that can put patients at risk for CIN. By identifying people at risk and initiating preventative measures the risk of developing nephropathy can be reduced.²⁹

In our study, we observed that in patients with low Hb, the mean serum creatinine level was 1.04±0.23 mg/dl at baseline, which was increased to 1.48±0.43 mg/dl after 48 hours of PCI. In patients with normal Hb, the mean creatinine level was 1.07±0.22 mg/dl, which was increased to 1.31±0.27 mg/dl (p<0.05). In patients with low Hb, CIN was positive in 17 (34.0%) cases while in patients with normal Hb 8 (16.0%) cases had CIN (p<0.05). In patients with low Hb, the mean albuminuria level was 40.88±7.27 mg/g at baseline, which was increased to 47.34±13.81 mg/dl after 24 hours. In patients with

normal Hb, the mean albuminuria level was 38.36±4.94 mg/g at baseline, which was increased to 43.43±9.79 mg/g after 24 hours (p>0.05). CIN was positive in 20 (40.0%) cases in patients with low Hb while in 9 (18.0%) cases they had normal Hb (p<0.05).

Some previous studies have not found Low hemoglobin levels as the problematic aspect for developing CIN.⁸ However Xu et al., reported in a study that a low amount of hemoglobin is the independent risk factor for CIN, which occurred in 5% of patients with normal hemoglobin levels and 14.7% of patients with low hemoglobin levels (relative risk, 3.07; P 0.01).¹³ which is concordant to our current study.

It also adhered to the finding of a study conducted by Xu J et al that the greatest risk factor for causing CIN is the concentration of contrast media infused. Low Hemoglobin was found to be the second highest risk factor for CIN. In the current study, serum creatinine level has found significant change after administering contrast media for PCI and Albuminuria was not found statistically significant.

A study showed that a low level of Hemoglobin became a contributing factor for causing CIN and risk is (3.07,95% CI, 1.69-5.56; P<0.01), and it was second to contrast media volume ≥150ml. Poor prognosis and death rate in patients are often associated with a low level of Hemoglobin¹⁶

Another study reported that when the Hemoglobin level is less than the normal range, there is increased

mortality due to dose-dependent contrast media.¹⁴ With each unit reduced in HB there is a 2.5 times chance of mortality with CIN. In patients with low Hb, there is also the risk of myocardial infarction and stable angina as reported by a study conducted by Shah et al.⁷

Patients who developed CIN usually have elevated levels of serum creatinine within 3-5 days after administration of contrast medium which return to the baseline level following enough hydration within 1-3 weeks.³² Renal functions of the patients can be assessed through an increase in serum creatinine and glomerular filtration rate. Those patients who have a low level of Hemoglobin despite normal renal function have more risk to develop CIN.¹⁰

Study reported that anemia is a common finding among many hospitalized patients including cardiac catheterization patients. Anemic patients are at increased risk of developing CIN especially with altered level of albumin in body. Anemic patients who developed CIN also found to have significant albuminuria ≥ 1 g/day establishing the possible relationship between albuminuria and CIN.¹⁰ Studies also revealed that CIN is highly associated with increase serum creatinine and albuminuria among anemic patients.¹² However Multiple studies are still required to establish whether albuminuria is a diagnostic marker of CIN or is an independent risk factor of developing contrast induced nephropathy. Therefore, serum creatinine is considered most effective marker in diagnosing CIN among the anemic patients who underwent percutaneous coronary intervention.

Conclusion

The study was carried out to determine the prevalence of contrast-induced nephropathy (CIN) among patients with a baseline normal hemoglobin (Hb) and low hemoglobin and assess how the serum creatinine and albuminuria levels are used as biomarkers to diagnose CIN. The results obtained showed that low Hb levels were statistically related to occurrence of CIN whereby 34 percent of anemic patients had CIN whereas only 16 percent of the non anemic patients developed CIN. It is consistent with what other researchers have found before that anemia is a risk factor that is independent of CIN and this can be attributed to the fact that renal

tissues are deprived of adequate oxygen supply, and thus contributing to the enhanced severe effects of contrast-induced hypoxic injury.

In this group, serum creatinine was a more dependable biomarker of CIN compared with albuminuria. Though the levels of both markers revealed elevation after PCI, the level of serum creatinine hiked meaningfully ($p < 0.05$); however, albuminuria lacked the discriminating power ($p > 0.05$). This implies that serum creatinine has continued to be the gold standard in the early detection of CIN in clinical practice especially among anemic patients. There was also the effect of procedural factors including contrast volume (>150 mL) that further increased the danger of CIN in patients with low Hb concentration.

The findings demonstrate the significance of risk stratification done ahead of the procedures, particularly to lessen CIN in anemic individuals. Such preventative measures as maximization of Hb levels, minimization of contrast volume and proper hydration might also help reduce the number of occurrences of this complication substantially. The paper also makes the point that one should pay careful attention to monitoring of renal functioning after PCI, especially in high-risk groups.

The study was however limited in that it was single center based and they considered the levels of Hb without relating it to underlying kidney diseases. It is suggested to conduct future multicenter, with larger cohorts study to prove these findings and investigate the importance of different biomarkers, e.g., neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin (NGAL) or cystatin C, in diagnosis of CIN. Studies on the correction of anemia before the PCI may also serve to portray the idea of diminishing the rates of CIN incidence.

Therefore, it can be concluded that this study presents the increased risk of CIN in anemic patients receiving PCI and reneutralizes that serum creatinine was identified as the most crucial biomarker at the initial stage of CIN. The results support the development of personalized preventative measures and enhanced surveillance in the high-risk populations to enhance clinical performance. Future studies are justified to increase the risk evaluation and look into new treatment methods so as to reduce the risk of CIN among vulnerable groups.

Limitations

The current study had some limitations described:

1. The study was only conducted in a single center in the Cardiology Department of Mayo Hospital.
2. The study only selected patients having Hemoglobin levels rather than identifying any kidney diseases.

Recommendations

1. It was recommended to conduct a future study in multiple hospitals to analyze better results.
2. It was recommended to diagnose kidney diseases for identifying further results of contrast on the kidney.

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